

A Novel and Robust GreenSoul-ed Lighting Controller

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Abstract—In this paper a novel and robust lighting controller with green soul has been presented. The GreenSoul-ed device is a fully autonomous and automated controller, which can control the lights in a building space without compromising users' comfort preferences. It can automatically dim the lights achieving users' preferences in real-time through a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controlling mechanism. To this end, it is equipped with a luminance sensor, as well as with embedded intelligence, while the processing and the decision making is performed on the controller (FoG computing). Furthermore, it supports a variety of functionalities, such as profiles, schedules, timezones, etc., while it is fully parameterized through its web interface. The preliminary experimental results has shown that the proposed GreenSoul-ed lighting controller can achieve more than 75% electricity savings of lighting in a building.

Index Terms—lighting controller, visual comfort, PID

I. INTRODUCTION

Global energy consumption is steadily increasing over the past years. Lighting accounts for 20% of the global electricity consumption [1]. Since most of the electricity is generated from fossil fuels, it leads to pollution and global warming. In an effort to reduce electricity consumption, new lighting technologies have been proposed. LED (lighting-emitting diode) seems to be the preferred technology to replace the current lighting systems as LED light bulbs may consume up to 75% less energy compared to incandescent and their lifespan is 25 times more [2]. Furthermore, the cost of the LED lighting has significantly dropped in the last years [3].

In an effort to further reduce electricity consumption a light dimmer can be utilized. Standard light switches have only two conditions: ON and OFF. Replacing a standard light switch with a dimmer helps to reduce electricity consumption and therefore the bill costs, the pollution and global warming. Also, dimming LED light bulbs prolong their life [4]. Thus, a huge effort has been made during the last years for incorporating dimming usage in the lighting systems.

Market has a small variety of smart dimmer products with embedded intelligence. An interesting remote switching product named Belkin WeMo switch [5], [6] is available to the market. The WeMo switch can be connected to an existing Wi-Fi network and allows the control of the lights over voice or through a mobile application. It supports schedules so as to turn ON/OFF the lights at sunrise/sunset and night mode operation for dimming the lights during specific times. The

physical user interface of the device supports only turning ON/OFF lights or dim them to a selected value. It does not display the luminance of the room nor the power consumption, while user profiles are not supported. A similar to Belkin WeMos dimmer is the Leviton Devora [7], which shares similar functionalities and restrictions.

Another interesting lighting controller is the Koo geek KH03 light dimmer [8]. It can be connected to existing Wi-Fi network and control the lights via voice or a mobile application. It can also monitor real-time, daily and monthly electric power consumption. As with the Belkin WeMos, the Koo geek KH03 seems to have the same constraints. It works with a specific type of hardware for control, the Apple HomeKit and it also needs a mobile app. The physical interface is limited, as it supports the same functionalities with WeMos. Finally, scheduling for turning the lights ON/OFF is not supported.

Fibaro [9] is also offering a solution for light dimming. Their product called Dimmer-2 is a lights' dimming device, which can replace an existing light switch. It consists of light control unit, an energy meter and a wireless communication system. The device is capable of toggling on/off and changing the brightness of the lights via an Android/iOS app. It also supports voice control. It does not feature a luminance sensor and thus a closed loop control of the lights based on ambient light is not possible. In addition, an LCD for outputting information about current preferences/ light status is not available, so the user must use an external device to control the lights. Dimmer-2 support incandescent, halogen and dimmable LED lamps but it does not support 1-10V dimming protocol for use with an external ballast. Schedule based turn on/off the lights is missing too.

Eltako [10] has a wide range of products for dimming the lights. Most of them however support dimming via a rotary switch. The dimmer can be configured for the maximum and minimum brightness level that the lights can deliver and also the dimming speed. They do not offer any smart solution like remote control via smartphone or PC, nor automatic control of the lights based on schedules.

Kasa HS220 [11] is tp-link solution offers LED lights dimming capabilities, Wi-Fi communication, scheduling, 3 button input interface and 7 LED used as brightness indicators. The device can be controlled also via an Android/iOS app. There is also the "gentle off" functionality that will fade the

lights for a configured duration of time.

In this paper, the proposed smart light dimmer is capable of sensing the luminance of the space, where it is installed and dim lights based on the preferred luminance of the user. In case of a luminance change, the device will compensate by changing the output of the lamp in a closed-loop control until the luminance reaches the selected value.

The proposed controller supports multiple profiles with separate luminance values for day and night for each profile. Every day the sunset and sunrise time is fetched, based on the location of the device, which is automatically acquired from the internet.

The smart dimmer also features a Human Interface Device (HID), which enables the user to read information on the LCD display (luminance, lamp status, power consumption, selected profile, time) and physically interact with the device with the help of 3 input buttons. Control of the device can also be achieved through the device's local webserver that enable the user to connect without using special equipment. Every device with a web browser can connect. Finally, the proposed light controller is compliant with dimmable LED light bulbs and with existing dimmable ballasts supporting the 1-10V protocol.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the proposed lighting device, while Section III describes the main functionality of the proposed system. Section IV describes the user interface of the proposed system. Experimental results are presented in Section V and conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. GREENSOUL-ED LIGHTING DEVICE

The GreenSoul-ed lighting device is a WiFi-enabled device capable of keeping the visual comfort (luminance in a space) in a space stable over the course of the day (and night). The user defines the desirable comfort levels, while the device measures in real-time the luminance in the space and automatically adjusts (dim) the lighting sources so as to achieve the desired visual comfort according to the user preferences.

The GreenSoul-ed lighting device provides the ability to the user to define the desired visual comfort levels in lux (namely to define a lighting profile). In other words, the user through the device menu can define the lux he/she prefers to have in the space. The device supports different levels for the day and night visual comforts, since the human visual sense perceives the luminance completely differently during the day and the night. In the sequence, the device gets the space luminance levels in lux through an embedded luminance sensor. The measurement of the sensor is compared with the user's luminance preferences instantly. In the case of a value difference, then the GreenSoul-ed lighting device dims the lighting sources so as the real measurements of the luminance sensor (real luminance in the space) to converge with the user's already defined lighting profile. For example, if the luminance in the space is above the desired one (i.e. user profile), then the controller dims down the light sources through the dimmer circuit in order to achieve the preferred values. This convergent of the real space luminance to the user profiles is achieved

through the Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) Controller embedded in the GreenSoul-ed lighting device (see Section III).

Fig. 1. GreenSoul-ed lighting device main components

The main parts of the GreenSoul-ed lighting device, as depicted in Figure 1, are:

- **Digital ambient light sensor:** The ambient light sensor is an optical sensor that converts the total luminous flux incident on its surface area (measured in lux) in digital format. It gives an indication to the perception of the intensity of the light by the human eye. The lux value is sent to the perception of the micro-controller unit, which periodically gets this value from the sensor.
- **WiFi micro-controller unit:** Micro-controller unit (MCU) is responsible for the logic and control of the system and in combination with the integrated Wi-Fi controller used for communication, it consist the “brains” of the device.

MCU periodically gets the ambient lux value from the sensor and based on a Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) algorithm calculates the dimming level of the lighting sources according to the lighting profile defined by the user and the current luminance read by the sensor. Furthermore, integrated Wi-Fi functionality enables for remote operation of the device through the creation of a local web-server. The device is able to connect to an existing Wi-Fi network and creates a web-server that can be used for further configuration of the device. If the available Wi-Fi network has an Internet connection, the device can fetch the current date, time and timezone from an online service, as well as the sunrise and sunset time for the current day based on the location.

- **AC phase cut dimmer controller:** The AC dimmer controller is responsible for dimming the lighting source of the space to a desired level. The voltage applied as input at the dimmer controlling the light intensity. A pulse

width modulated signal from the MCU is converted to a DC voltage at a resistor-capacitor (RC) filter, which is connected to the dimmer circuit.

If the controller detects zero voltage input (0V), which is the case where the lights are off, then it automatically enters in a low power mode in order to reduce the power consumption.

The dimming of the lights is achieved through the switching part of the circuit, while another switch is responsible for switching the control of the lights from manual ON/OFF to MCU/Dimmer mode.

- **Human Interface Device (HID):** The HID is the module for the interaction between the user and the device. It consists of a button array for the user input and the LCD display for the output. User can get information about the current luminance of the room, the selected user profile and the preferred lux of the profile, the dimming status of the light source and an approximation of the power consumption on (LCD). They can also interact with the device via the input interface, which consists of the three buttons for menu navigation.

III. PROPORTIONAL INTEGRAL DERIVATIVE (PID) CONTROLLER

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the automatic lighting sources control

The automatic lighting source control is the main procedure of the proposed GreenSoul-ed lighting device. The flow chart of this procedure is illustrated in Figure 2.

The MCU gets the ambient lux value of the space where it is located. In the sequence, this value is compared with the lighting profile defined by the user, and if there is a difference, the MCU calculates the dimming levels of the lighting device through a Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) algorithm. This functionality is periodically performed.

A PID controller is a control loop feedback mechanism widely used in industrial control systems and a variety of other applications requiring continuously modulated control. A PID algorithm continuously calculates an error value $e(t)$ as the difference between a desired setpoint (SP) and a measured process variable (PV) and applies a correction based on proportional, integral, and derivative terms (denoted P , I , and D respectively).

The PID algorithm has the ability to use the three control terms of proportional, integral and derivative influence on the controller output to apply accurate and optimal control. The block diagram (Figure 3) shows the principles of how these

Fig. 3. A block diagram of a PID algorithm in a feedback loop.

terms are generated and applied. It continuously calculates an error value $e(t)$ as the difference between the desired lighting profile $L_p(t)$ and the measured space luminance $L_l(t)$, and it applies a correction based on proportional, integral, and derivative terms. The controller attempts to minimize the error over time by adjusting a control variable $u(t)$, such as the opening of a control valve, to a new value determined by a weighted sum of the control terms.

In this model:

- Term P is proportional to the current value of the $L_p(t) - L_l(t)$ error $e(t)$. Thus, this parameter accounts for present values of the error.
- Term I accounts for past values of the $L_p(t) - L_l(t)$ error and integrates them over time to produce the I term. For example, if there is a residual $L_p(t) - L_l(t)$ error after the application of proportional control, the integral term seeks to eliminate the residual error by adding a control effect due to the historic cumulative value of the error. When the error is eliminated, the integral term will cease to grow. This will result in the proportional effect diminishing as the error decreases, but this is compensated for by the growing integral effect. Thus, this parameter accounts for past values of the error.
- Term D is a best estimate of the future trend of the $L_p(t) - L_l(t)$ error, based on its current rate of change. It is sometimes called “anticipatory control”, as it is effectively seeking to reduce the effect of the $L_p(t) - L_l(t)$ error by exerting a control influence generated by the rate of error change. The more rapid the change, the greater the controlling or dampening effect. Thus, this parameter accounts for possible future values of the error, based on its current rate of change.

Thus, the goal of the PID algorithm is to minimize the parameter $u(t)$, which mathematically can be expressed as follows [12], [13]:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t') dt' + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}, \quad (1)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d , all non-negative, denote the coefficients for the proportional, integral, and derivative terms respectively.

IV. USER INTERACTION WITH THE GREENSOUL-ED LIGHTING DEVICE

The settings and preferences of the GreenSoul-ed lighting device can be adjusted through:

- the Human Interface Device (HID) and the LCD display;
- the local Wi-Fi web-server.

A. Human Interface Device (HID)

The integrated buttons and display are both part of the Human Interface Device (HID), which enables the user to read information on the LCD display and physically interact with the device with the help of three input buttons. The HID provides an integrated menu, where the user is able to:

- view the activated profile and the profile's lux (day/night);
- view the current luminance of the room;
- select and activate specific profile;
- view the light source status (dim percentage, ON/OFF);
- toggle the lights and dimming ON/OFF
- change the day or night lux of the active profile;
- find the local IP address of the device.

For advanced capabilities of the device, the local web-server can be used (Section IV-B).

B. Web Interface

For advanced capabilities of the device, the local web-server can be used. Through the interface of the server (Figure 4), the user can:

Info

Device Hostname: GreenSoul Lights gs-677
 Device Local IP: 160.40.49.180
 Firmware Version: 0.1

SSID: WLAN-ITI-HOME
 Lights ID: 9
 Time: 17/05/2018 19:34:13 (Day)
 Region: Europe/Athens

Last Reset: Software/System restart
 Boot Time: 15/05/2018 15:40:26
 Free RAM: 11960 bytes

Configuration

Active Profile: default
 Current Lux: 54
 Profile Lux: 70
 Lights: DIM 4.6W (57%)
 Sunrise: 6:8 - Sunset: 20:40

Profiles Schedule Timezone

Settings

PID MQTT Location

Lights

Toggle lights off Toggle dimming off

Device

Logs Advanced Restart

Fig. 4. Main menu of the web interface

- *see the current status of the lighting device:* In this section, the user can see the unique ID of the device, as well as its IP and the firmware version. Also, the user can see the Wi-Fi network the device is connected to, the current timezone and information of the active profile (e.g. the name of the profile and the desired lux). Finally, the current lux of the room, the dimming level of the lights, and the sunrise/ sunset times are displayed. Sunrise/sunset times define the automatic swap of the profiles day/night preferred lux.
- *create, delete, change, activate profiles:* On the profile page, the user can see the profiles already stored in the device. The user can update a profile (i.e. its friendly name and the day/night desired lux values), as well as delete it. Finally, the user can activate a profile through this page, enforcing the lighting device to operate with this profile. Finally, a new profile can be created.
- *create, delete, change, activate scheduling:* On the schedule page, the user can check the device's schedules, i.e. the name, trigger time, repetition, action of the schedule and of course if it should be enabled or not. Through this page, the user can delete, enable or disable and update an existing schedule, as well as create new ones. A schedule can switch on or off the lighting device at a specific time with repetition. Thus, the user can define the optimal usage of the lighting services, having the optimal luminance in the room, without bothering when to switch the lights or if they are left on during the nights or the weekends.
- *define the timezone:* With this functionality the user can manually select the timezone of the region that the device is located. If the device is connected to the Internet, then this information is automatically filled by the device.
- *change the PID parameter configuration:* The PID parameters (i.e. K_p , K_i and K_d) can be defined and updated. Changing these parameters, the user can change the behavior of the lighting device, e.g. how quick it reacts to luminance changes, how quick and accurate will try the device to converge/ adjust the dimming of the lighting in order to catch the desired luminance levels, etc.
- *change the MQTT parameters:* The lighting device is programmed so as to be able to bypass the embedded lux sensor, and operate with luminance information received by an external source/ sensor. This sensor sends the luminance values to an MQTT broker, where the lighting device can read and operate on real time.
- *change the location of the device:* With this functionality the user can manually define the location of the device. If there is an Internet connection, this information is automatically fetched and filled. This information is important for the sunrise and sunset definition, which is different for every region, and it affects the device day/ night mode operation.
- *turn lights ON/OFF:* The user can remotely switch on/off the light sources.

- *toggle lighting dimming ON/OFF*: The user can remotely toggle the lighting dimming level for the light sources.
- *check the log of the device*: The lighting device logs everything (e.g. every change through the menu, changes in the operation, etc.) with high details in a log file, which the user can check.
- *change the Wi-Fi settings*: The user can define the WiFi settings, i.e. the network SSID and the password, so as the device to be able to connect to the Internet.
- *update the firmware*: The device supports the remotely firmware update without requiring the physical presentation of a technician.

C. Use case

In this Section, a scenario will be described, presenting the capabilities and usage of the proposed GreenSoul-ed lighting device. There is an office with two employees, who forget the lights switched on during the nights and weekends, while they have them always on during the working hours, even when the outside sources (e.g. sun) provides enough luminance in the office. The working hours of the office are 09:00 am to 18:00 pm during working days (Monday to Friday). The office is equipped with LED lights of 50 Watt in total.

The director of the company decides to change the conventional switches with the proposed GreenSoul-ed lighting switches. The device is installed and an Internet connection is provided to it, so as to automatically receives the location, the timezone, and the sunrise/sunset times every day. The office lighting profile, after a discussion with the employees for their preferences, is set equal to 180 during the day and 50 for the nights. Also, a schedule is set up, which switches on the lights at 9:00 am and switches them off at 18:00 every afternoon, while during the weekends remain off.

The savings that can be achieved by the proposed lighting device at the electricity, is straight forward to the use of the lighting, so let us introduce some use cases:

- The employees forget the lights switched on during the nights and weekends, while they have them always on during the working hours. Utilizing the conventional lighting system, the electricity that is needed is 8,400 *kWh* for a whole week, while the proposed system with a set of 100% dimming level all the time is 2,250 *kWh* for the same period of time. Thus, a 73,2% is achieved at the electricity for the specific office.
- The employees forget the lights switched on during the nights and weekends, while they have them always on during the working hours. Utilizing the conventional lighting system, the electricity that is needed is 8,400 *kWh* for a whole week, while the proposed system achieves the desired luminance levels with a 50% dimming level all the time. In this case, it is required only 1,125 *kWh* for a week. Thus, a 86,6% is achieved at the electricity for the specific office.
- The employees forget the lights switched on during the nights but not during the weekends, while they have them always on during the working hours. Utilizing the

conventional lighting system, the electricity that is needed is 6,000 *kWh* for a whole week, while the proposed system achieves the desired luminance levels with a 50% dimming level. In this case, it is required only 1,125 *kWh* for a week, which means that it can achieved a 81,3% savings at the electricity for the specific office.

- The employees switch off the lights during the nights and weekends, but they have them always on during the working hours. Utilizing the conventional lighting system, the electricity that is needed is 2,250 *kWh* for a whole week, while the proposed system achieves the desired luminance levels with a 50% dimming level. In this case, it is required only 1,125 *kWh* for a week, which means that it can achieved a 50,0% savings at the electricity for the specific office.

Thus, having installed the proposed lighting system, it can be achieved more than 50% savings at the electricity, without compromising the comfort of the users.

Finally, one can claim that the proposed lighting device is not just another lighting controller, but it is an Internet-of-Thing (IoT) with embedded intelligence, which can achieve stable environmental conditions in a building regarding the visual comfort and remarkable energy savings.

Fig. 5. Luminance and lights power for a full working day (desired comfort levels equal to 120 for the day and 50 for the night)

Fig. 6. Luminance and lights power for a full working day (desired comfort levels equal to 100 for the day and 50 for the night)

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The GreenSoul-ed lighting controller has been thoroughly tested for more than two weeks in an office at CERN premises. The office was equipped with two LED lights of 11

Fig. 7. Luminance and lights power for 15 consecutive days

Watts each (22 Watts in total). The schedule is set to switch on the lights at 9:00 am and switch them off at 21:00, while the luminance profile has been set to various values depending on the experiment.

Figure 5 illustrates the luminance against lights' power (in watts) for a full day (working hours). The specific day the sunrise and sunset times were at 06:34 and 20:18 respectively, while the scheduler switched them on at 09:00 am and switched them off at 21:00. One can notice that the lights were not operating during the whole day, since the controller dimmed them according to the luminance of the office. When a cloud decreases the luminance of the external sources, and as a consequence the luminance in the office, then the proposed lighting controller dims the lights in order to achieve the desired visual comfort (desired luminance). That is, every time that the luminance in the office falls below a threshold (120 lux during the day and 50 lux for the night for the specific experiment), the controller dims the lights in order to "correct" the office luminance and achieve the desired level. Thus, one can see that the luminance in the office varies according to the cloudiness, while the controller follows these changes and tries to keep a constant luminance in the office (which of course is directly depended on the lights installed in the office). Finally, having in mind that the lights were switched on in the office during all working hours of the day, the energy consumption needed for the lights with a conventional controller would be 264 Wh , while the proposed controller consumed only 51,93 Wh for the whole day, achieving energy savings up to 80,33%.

Another example of the operation of the proposed lighting controller is shown in Figure 6. In this case the desired comfort levels have been set equal to 100 for the day and 50 for the night. The energy consumption consumed by the lights in this day was 61.15 Wh , achieving energy savings up to 76,84%.

Figure 7 illustrates the luminance in the office and the power of the lights for 15 consecutive days. The desired comfort levels have been set equal to 100 for the day and

50 for the night, while the scheduler switched on and off the lights at 09:00 am and 21:00 respectively every day. The energy consumption that is needed with a conventional lighting controller is estimated to 3960 Wh , while in the current installation, the proposed controller forced the lights to consume only 807,19 Wh with the same or very similar visual comfort, achieving energy savings up to 79,62%. Based on these measurements, we can assume that the proposed lighting controller can achieve energy savings more than 75% in an office, without compromising the comfort of the users.

Table I presents the electricity consumption (in MWh) of lighting for the residential and non-residential sector along the EU countries¹. Making the assumption that the lighting can be controlled by a system like the proposed one, the savings at the electricity consumption could be at least 25% (lets take the most pessimistic scenario). Table I presents these savings, as well as the savings in €, and tons CO_2 equivalent. One can notice that in both residential and non-residential sectors along the EU, the energy savings could be around 63 TWh , 6,5 billion €, and 47 Gtons CO_2 in a single year.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper a novel lighting controller has been presented. It is a fully autonomous and automated controller, which can control the lights in a building space without human intervention and without disturbing the users or their comfort preferences. The lighting controller adjust/ dim the lights so as to achieve the desired comfort levels in a space in real-time. Furthermore, the proposed controller supports schedules, so as to automatically switch on and off the lights at specific times. In other words, the proposed lighting controller has embedded intelligence, while the overall processing and the decision making performed locally (FoG computing), on the controller. The preliminary experimental results has shown the proposed lighting controller can achieve savings more than

¹<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/eu-buildings-database> (last access May 2018)

TABLE I
ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF LIGHTING IN RESIDENTIAL AND NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS FOR EACH COUNTRY IN EU, AND THE CORRESPONDING SAVINGS IN kWh, €, AND TONS CO₂ BY A SYSTEM LIKE THE PROPOSED ONE

Country	Consumption (kWh)		Savings (kWh)		Savings (€)		Savings (tons CO ₂)	
	Residential	Non-residential	Residential	Non-residential	Residential	Non-residential	Residential	Non-residential
Austria	1.628.200	2.907.500	407.050	726.875	40.705.000	72.687.500	302.845	540.795
Belgium	2.442.300	3.837.900	610.575	959.475	61.057.500	95.947.500	454.268	713.849
Bulgaria	581.500	1.511.900	145.375	377.975	14.537.500	37.797.500	108.159	281.213
Croatia	581.500	930.400	145.375	232.600	14.537.500	23.260.000	108.159	173.054
Cyprus	232.600	232.600	58.150	58.150	5.815.000	5.815.000	43.264	43.264
Czech Republic	814.100	2.442.300	203.525	610.575	20.352.500	61.057.500	151.423	454.268
Denmark	3.256.400	2.209.700	814.100	552.425	81.410.000	55.242.500	605.690	411.004
Estonia	348.900	348.900	87.225	87.225	8.722.500	8.722.500	64.895	64.895
Finland	2.093.400	2.326.000	523.350	581.500	52.335.000	58.150.000	389.372	432.636
France	9.187.700	19.538.400	2.296.925	4.884.600	229.692.500	488.460.000	1.708.912	3.634.142
Germany	12.793.000	47.450.400	3.198.250	11.862.600	319.825.000	1.186.260.000	2.379.498	8.825.774
Greece	1.977.100	2.791.200	494.275	697.800	49.427.500	69.780.000	367.741	519.163
Hungary	2.558.600	1.977.100	639.650	494.275	63.965.000	49.427.500	475.900	367.741
Ireland	1.395.600	1.511.900	348.900	377.975	34.890.000	37.797.500	259.582	281.213
Italy	9.652.900	18.259.100	2.413.225	4.564.775	241.322.500	456.477.500	1.795.439	3.396.193
Latvia	465.200	465.200	116.300	116.300	11.630.000	11.630.000	86.527	86.527
Lithuania	814.100	581.500	203.525	145.375	20.352.500	14.537.500	151.423	108.159
Luxembourg	116.300	465.200	29.075	116.300	2.907.500	11.630.000	21.632	86.527
Malta	116.300	232.600	29.075	58.150	2.907.500	5.815.000	21.632	43.264
Netherlands	3.256.400	5.815.000	814.100	1.453.750	81.410.000	145.375.000	605.690	1.081.590
Poland	697.800	7.908.400	174.450	1.977.100	17.445.000	197.710.000	129.791	1.470.962
Portugal	1.628.200	2.791.200	407.050	697.800	40.705.000	69.780.000	302.845	519.163
Romania	1.628.200	1.628.200	407.050	407.050	40.705.000	40.705.000	302.845	302.845
Slovakia	348.900	1.395.600	87.225	348.900	8.722.500	34.890.000	64.895	259.582
Slovenia	232.600	581.500	58.150	145.375	5.815.000	14.537.500	43.264	108.159
Spain	8.141.000	13.141.900	2.035.250	3.285.475	203.525.000	328.547.500	1.514.226	2.444.393
Sweden	4.070.500	4.186.800	1.017.625	1.046.700	101.762.500	104.670.000	757.113	778.745
UK	11.281.100	23.027.400	2.820.275	5.756.850	282.027.500	575.685.000	2.098.285	4.283.096
Total	82.340.400	170.495.800	20.585.100	42.623.950	2.058.510.000	4.262.395.000	15.315.314	31.712.219

75% in a building, without compromising the users' comfort. Thus, one can claim that the proposed lighting controller is equipped with green soul, that it is a GreenSoul-ed device.

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